

ZDZW

Newsletter n°1 – April 2023

HORIZON EUROPE Programme GA No. 101057404

@ZDZW_Project

ZDZW Project

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Welcome to the first ZDZW project newsletter!

ZDZW is a collaborative research project addressing the **need for optimization of product quality control and monitoring in manufacturing processes, minimizing waste and environmental impacts**, as well as the need for rework procedures and component life increase.

ZDZW aims to **develop advanced cost-efficient inspection technologies** compatible with digitally enabled manufacturing processes **using advanced artificial-intelligence techniques**. **ZDZW** Inspection Solutions cover product integrity assessment, visual and geometric properties inspection, and thermal processes monitoring and control and will be applied in six pilots across different industrial sectors and processes.

This first newsletter will outline the main objectives of the project. Future editions will provide updates on the progress of the work and project-related news and events.

More info is available on the website (www.zdzw-project.eu).

The potential benefits of non-destructive inspection

Non-destructive inspection (NDI) technologies for quality control and process monitoring allow inspection and evaluation of different measurable quantities within production processes to assure that product quality and process performance meet expected levels. An **effective integration of new NDI** technologies being able to inspect the required product characteristics, compute key performance metrics and evaluate complex quality parameters, is necessary **to achieve the actual benefits which sustainable smart factories aim to achieve**.

[Watch the introductory video of ZDZW](#)

Funded by the
European Union

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The ZDZW APPROACH

Monitor: to facilitate in-line inspection services to evaluate process and product quality

Control: to maximize the number of first-time-right (FTR) parts while simultaneously reducing the need of reworks and resulting scrap

Rework & Repair: to enhance reworking process of components, reducing the time spent by rework operators needed to reprocess

Digital Ecosystem: ZDZW will integrate with relevant existing initiatives providing interoperability, interlinking, security, data reliability and digital platforms;

Sustainability: ZDZW will demonstrate its (ZD) zero-waste (ZW) approach in different industrial sectors of key importance for global sustainability

The ZDZW CONSORTIUM

27 Partners

11 Countries

12 Industrial Partners

ZDZW consortium consists of a **multidisciplinary team of 27 partners** from **11 EU & Associated countries**, providing a multi-stakeholder approach and covering the whole value chain through a **combination of technology developers** (Research Centres and universities) **and technology providers** (SMEs or large companies), end-users (large manufacturing companies in the automotive components, food & beverages, home appliances, eHealth or wind sector), **experts in dissemination, business cases / exploitation, safety, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), social science and standardization.**

www.zdzw-project.eu

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What is happening in ZDZW project?

3
Conference posters

1
Journal paper

9
Events attended/
Presented [fairs,
conferences, workshops]

Scientific publications

CONFERENCE PUBLICATIONS

National Optics Congress (Danish Optical Society)

Diode-Pumped MIR Supercontinuum Source for applications within non-destructive testing [Poster]

December 2022

National Optics Congress (Danish Optical Society)

~2.7 um Er-doped fluoride pulsed fiber laser source [Poster]

December 2022

National Optics Congress (Danish Optical Society)

High energy ultrafast laser generation from a Tm-doped Mamyshev oscillator [Poster]

December 2022

JOURNAL PAPERS

Wind Energy

Non-Destructive and Contactless Defect Detection inside Leading Edge Coatings for Wind Turbine Blades using Optical Coherence Tomography [Accepted]

November 2022

Christian Petersen, Søren Fæster, Jakob Bech, Kristine Jespersen, Niels Israelsen, Ole Bang

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What is happening in ZDZW project?

Events

Participation in A&T Automation & testing fair

21/02/2022

Attendance at CONNECTED FACTORIES & EFPE Projects Final event

24/11/2022

Participation in Zero-Defect manufacturing workshop by 4ZDM cluster and ZDM sub-platform under manufacture

23/11/2022

Attendance at Digital Transformation Summit

24/10/2022

Participation in i4MS Stakeholders event

19/10/2022

Attendance at ITAP 2022

Industrial Transformation Asia-Pacific

18/10/2022

Attendance at VISION 2022
Trade for machine vision

06/10/2022

Attendance at the 16th World Congress on Engineering Asset management

05/10/2022

Up-coming EVENTS

Digital Manufacturing Industrial Summit (DMIS)

24-27th April 2023

Valencia, Spain

We would like to invite you to the **DMIS** which will connect stakeholders from **industry, academia** and **policy makers** to facilitate the debate on the digital transformation of European Industry.

DMIS is organised by the ZDMP **Zero Defects Manufacturing Platform**, and many other partners such as ZDZW.

Registration is free at: [DMIS2023.org](https://www.DMIS2023.org)

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Do you know the ZDZW COMMUNITY?

The [ZDZW community](#) is the perfect place to **interact** & **foster cooperation**, and it's a **rich ecosystem** of active members to find **synergies**

Technical content will be published periodically by each partner, according to their field of expertise.

[Take a look at the first publication!](#)

Join us to keep you up to date with the ZDZW project evolution!

ZERO DEFECT WASTE

IMAGING A WORLD WHERE **ZERO WASTE** IS PRODUCED, **AMBITIOUS BUT NOT IMPOSSIBLE**

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DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION

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THANKS BY STOPPING BY!

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